

Appendix of “Detecting Bad Smells in Use Case Descriptions”

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Abstract—This article is an appendix of our paper entitled “Detecting Bad Smells in Use Case Descriptions” to be published in proceedings of the 27th IEEE International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE’19) [1].

I. SELECTED USE CASE DESCRIPTIONS FOR INSPECTION

Table I shows the list of used use case descriptions that have been selected for the inspection of bad smells in them. In the table, the columns indicate the ID (ID), the name of the target use case (Name), the domain of the use case (Domain), the description when available (Description), the source information (Source), the numbers of basic steps (B), exception steps (E), and alternate steps (A). The descriptions U01–30 were used for the analysis in Section II in the original paper [1]. The descriptions U30–38 were used for the controlled experiment in Section III in the original paper [1]. Since the original name and description are in Japanese, we translated them into English. The domain information was not extracted from the sources but was derived by the authors. For the items that we retrieved the source information via a web search, the symbols explaining the way how they were searched are attached. We used both Google Search (Ⓔ) and Google Image Search (Ⓘ), and two different queries (Ⓔ and Ⓘ).

II. COMPARISON AMONG CATALOGUES

Table II shows our comparison result of smell catalogues. In the table, rows indicate smells defined in our paper, and columns indicate the smells defined in existing three catalogues: Phalp *et al.* [5], Törner *et al.* [6], and Anda and Sjøberg [7]. If a smell defined by us matches with a smell defined in other catalogues, the symbol ✓ is filled in the associated cell.

We show the smells defined in other three catalogues as follows.

P: Phalp et al. [5]:

- P01:** Coverage: Scope
- P02:** Coverage: Span
- P03:** Cogent: Text Order
- P04:** Cogent: Dependencies
- P05:** Cogent: Rational Answer
- P06:** Coherent
- P07:** Consistent Abstraction
- P08:** Consistent Structure: Variations

- P09:** Consistent Structure: Sequence
- P10:** Consistent Grammar
- P11:** Consideration of Alternatives: Separation
- P12:** Consideration of Alternatives: Viable
- P13:** Consideration of Alternatives: Numbering

T: Törner et al. [6]:

- T01:** Completeness: Missing element (C1)
- T02:** Completeness: Goal not achieved (C2)
- T03:** Correctness: Incorrect flow (C3)
- T04:** Correctness: Outside scope (C4)
- T05:** Consistency: Inconsistent step numbering (C5)
- T06:** Consistency: Irrelevant steps (C6)
- T07:** Consistency: Use Case Decomposition (C7)
- T08:** Readability: Misuse of alternative flows (C8)
- T09:** Unambiguity: Unclear alternative flow condition (C9)
- T10:** Unambiguity: Incorrect linguistics (C10)
- T11:** Level of detail (C11)
- T12:** Misuse of preconditions (C12)

A: Anda and Sjøberg [7]:

- A01:** *<Omissions, Actors>*: Human users or external entities that will interact with the system are not identified
- A02:** *<Omissions, Use cases>*: Required functionality is not described in use cases. Actors have goals that do not have corresponding use cases
- A03:** *<Omissions, Flow of events>*: Input or output for use cases is not described. Events that are necessary for understanding the use cases are missing
- A04:** *<Omissions, Variations>*: Variations that may occur when attempting to achieve the goal of a use case are not specified
- A05:** *<Omissions, Relation between use cases>*: Common functionality is not separated out in included use cases
- A06:** *<Omissions, Trigger, pre- and post-conditions>*: Trigger, pre- or post-conditions have been omitted
- A07:** *<Incorrect facts, Actors>*: Incorrect description of actors or wrong connection between actor and use case
- A08:** *<Incorrect facts, Use cases>*: Incorrect description of a use case
- A09:** *<Incorrect facts, Flow of events>*: Incorrect description of one or several events

- A10:** *⟨Incorrect facts, Variations⟩*: Incorrect description of a variation
- A11:** *⟨Incorrect facts, Trigger, pre- and post-conditions⟩*: Incorrect assumptions or results have led to incorrect pre- or post-conditions
- A12:** *⟨Inconsistencies, Actors⟩*: Description of actor is inconsistent with its behavior in use cases
- A13:** *⟨Inconsistencies, Use cases⟩*: Description is inconsistent with reaching the goal of the use case
- A14:** *⟨Inconsistencies, Flow of events⟩*: Events that are inconsistent with reaching the goal of the use case they are part of
- A15:** *⟨Inconsistencies, Variations⟩*: Variations that are inconsistent with the goal of the use case
- A16:** *⟨Inconsistencies, Relation between use cases⟩*: Inconsistencies between diagram and descriptions, inconsistent terminology, inconsistencies between use cases, or different level of granularity
- A17:** *⟨Inconsistencies, Trigger, pre- and post-conditions⟩*: Pre- or post-conditions are inconsistent with goal or flow of events
- A18:** *⟨Ambiguities, Actors⟩*: Too broadly defined actors or ambiguous description of actor
- A19:** *⟨Ambiguities, Use cases⟩*: Name of use case does not reflect the goal of the use case
- A20:** *⟨Ambiguities, Flow of events⟩*: Ambiguous description of events, perhaps because of too little detail
- A21:** *⟨Ambiguities, Variations⟩*: Ambiguous description of what leads to a particular variation
- A22:** *⟨Ambiguities, Trigger, pre- and post-conditions⟩*: Ambiguous description of trigger, pre- or post-condition
- A23:** *⟨Extraneous information, Actors⟩*: Actors that do not derive value from/provide value to the system
- A24:** *⟨Extraneous information, Use cases⟩*: Use cases with functionality outside the scope of the system or use cases that duplicate functionality
- A25:** *⟨Extraneous information, Flow of events⟩*: Superfluous steps or too much detail in steps
- A26:** *⟨Extraneous information, Variations⟩*: Variations that are outside the scope of the system
- A27:** *⟨Extraneous information, Trigger, pre- and post-conditions⟩*: Superfluous trigger, pre- or post-conditions

III. DEFINITION OF USE CASE DESCRIPTION SMELLS

All the definitions of bad smells in use case descriptions defined in our paper are as follows.

Name: Unordered Flow

Characteristic: *Ambiguity*

Scope: *Section*

Symptom: Some flows are not ordered correctly, and they lead to the difficulties in understanding the behavior of the use case.

How to Detect:

- The ID number (briefly ID) of a basic flow starts with 1? (*BasicFlowStartWith1?*)
- The ID of an alternate flow starts with 1? (*AlternateFlowStartWith1?*)
- The ID of an exception flow starts with 1? (*ExceptionFlowStartWith1?*)
- Each flow of a basic flow is numbered? (*BasicFlowNumbered?*)
- Each flow of an alternate flow is numbered? (*AlternateFlowNumbered?*)
- Each flow of an exception flow is numbered? (*ExceptionFlowNumbered?*)
- The numbering of a basic flow is incremented by 1? (*BasicFlowOrdered?*)
- The numbering of an alternate flow is incremented by 1? (*AlternateFlowOrdered?*)
- The numbering of an exception flow is incremented by 1? (*ExceptionFlowOrdered?*)

Name: Origin-Free Exception Flow

Characteristic: *Ambiguity*

Scope: *Section*

Symptom: The origin of an exception flow, i.e., the source of branching to the exception flow, is not specified. It leads to making it difficult to follow the overall flow of the use case.

How to Detect: It is described in the exception flow at which sentences the exception for branching to the exception flow may occur in the basic flow? (*ExceptionFlowsOriginDescribed?*)

Name: Origin-Free Alternate Flow

Characteristic: *Ambiguity*

Scope: *Section*

Symptom: The origin of an alternate flow, i.e., the source of branching to the alternate flow, is not specified. It leads to making it difficult to follow the overall flow of the use case.

How to Detect: It is described in the alternate flow at which sentences in the basic flow the alternate flow may start to be executed? (*AlternateFlowsOriginDescribed?*)

Name: Unclear Feasibility

Characteristic: *Sentence*

Scope: *Ambiguity*

Symptom: An action denoted by a sentence may be required to satisfy conditions before its execution, but these conditions cannot be certified to hold. For example, an action requires some input data for its execution, but their existence cannot be certified at the point of the sentence. It is necessary to walk through the flow that includes the sentence.

How to Detect: –

Name: Origin-Free Operation Result

Characteristic: *Ambiguity*

Scope: *Sentence*

Symptom: The sentence includes the description of the result of execution before, but it is not specified where the described result is obtained. It is time-consuming to explore the reference to the execution point where the result is generated.

How to Detect: –

Name: Sentence Interpretable as Multiple Meaning

Characteristic: *Ambiguity*

Scope: *Sentence*

Symptom: An action denoted by a sentence cannot be uniquely decided. It depends on readers of the sentence, and they may not be able to understand the sentence correctly.

How to Detect: –

Name: Pronoun

Characteristic: *Ambiguity*

Scope: *Word*

Symptom: The occurrence of a pronoun may provide ambiguity on what it denotes.

How to Detect: There is an occurrence of pronouns? (NOP > 0)

Name: Omitted Word

Characteristic: *Ambiguity*

Scope: *Word*

Symptom: Omitting a word may lead to the lack of the necessary information in a sentence, and it can be ambiguous.

How to Detect: –

Name: “Actor” Actor

Characteristic: *Ambiguity*

Scope: *Word*

Symptom: The subject of a sentence denoting an action is “Actor” and a concrete object who performs the action may not be uniquely decided, i.e., ambiguous.

How to Detect: There is an occurrence of the word “Actor” in a sentence? (NON(“Actor”) > 0)

Name: Unexplained Main Actor

Characteristic: *Ambiguity*

Scope: *Word*

Symptom: The word that is not “System” or that is not specified in Actor section is used as a subject of a sentence denoting an action. It is time-consuming to understand who is essentially an actor.

How to Detect: –

Name: Different Concepts by Same Word

Characteristic: *Ambiguity*

Scope: *Word*

Symptom: A word is used to represent different concepts. The meaning of the word is ambiguous.

How to Detect: –

Name: Omitted Attribute

Characteristic: *Ambiguity*

Scope: *Word*

Symptom: The operation to an object is represented in a sentence, but the operation is actually not to the object but its attribute. An object is confused with its attribute. It may cause misunderstanding of the meaning of the operation.

How to Detect: –

Name: Flow Does Not Meet Precondition

Characteristic: *Incorrectness*

Scope: *Section*

Symptom: A flow does not satisfy a precondition at starting its execution. In this case, the flow cannot be correctly executed.

How to Detect: –

Name: Postcondition Not Satisfied

Characteristic: *Incorrectness*

Scope: *Section*

Symptom: At the termination of the flow, a postcondition is not satisfied. In this case, the flow cannot be correctly executed.

How to Detect: –

Name: Name Does Not Explain Content

Characteristic: *Incorrectness*

Scope: *Section*

Symptom: The name of a use case does not represent its essential content. It causes its misunderstanding.

How to Detect: –

Name: Under or Over Condition

Characteristic: *Incorrectness*

Scope: *Section*

Symptom: Preconditions and/or postconditions include redundant conditions, or some of them are missing. In the case of redundant conditions, additional actions may be required to satisfy the redundant conditions. On the other hand, in the case of missing conditions, an action to satisfy the missing condition may also be missing. In both cases, the flow cannot be correct to the real execution and cannot satisfy the requirements.

How to Detect: –

Name: Much or Less Actors

Characteristic: *Incorrectness*

Scope: *Section*

Symptom: There is an actor in a flow, but it does not appear in the Actor section. On the other hand, there is an actor appearing in the Actor section, but it does not occur in the flow sections. In the former case, there are two possibilities: 1) an action performed by the actor is missing, or 2) the actor is redundant. In the latter case, it causes misunderstanding of the actor because of lacking information of the actor.

How to Detect: –

Name: Contradicted Sentences

Characteristic: *Incorrectness*

Scope: *Sentence*

Symptom: More than one sentence is contradicted to each other. Either of them may be incorrect.

How to Detect: –

Name: Behavior Ignores Condition

Characteristic: *Incorrectness*

Scope: *Sentence*

Symptom: An action denoted by a sentence is executed without satisfying its conditions that should hold before executing it. In this case, another action that should be executed before may be lacking, or the conditions may be wrong.

How to Detect: –

Name: Multiple Situations

Characteristic: *Granularity*

Scope: *Usecase*

Symptom: In a use case description of a use case, multiple different situations are assumed. The use case description is not decomposed at a sufficient level, and it should be decomposed into several use cases.

How to Detect: –

Name: Multiple Exception Flows at an Exception Branch Condition

Characteristic: *Granularity*

Scope: *Section*

Symptom: There are multiple exception flows which start with the same condition. It may cause a misunderstanding that different exceptions exist. It should be merged to a single exception flow.

How to Detect: Are there multiple occurrences of branches at the alphabetically same exception condition? (NOEFR > 1)

Name: Multiple Alternate Flows at an Alternate Branch Condition

Characteristic: *Granularity*

Scope: *Section*

Symptom: There are multiple alternate flows which start with the same condition. It may cause a misunderstanding that

different alternatives exist. It should be merged into a single alternate flow.

How to Detect: Are there multiple occurrences of branches at the alphabetically same alternate condition? (NOAFR > 0)

Name: Multiple Roles of an Actor

Characteristic: *Granularity*

Scope: *Section*

Symptom: The different roles are assigned to a word denoting an actor. It is difficult to understand which roles perform what actions. The different words should be adopted so that an actor is assigned to a single role.

How to Detect: –

Name: Multiple Actors of a Role

Characteristic: *Granularity*

Scope: *Section*

Symptom: The different words are used to represent one actor role. It causes a misunderstanding that these words may denote the different roles of actors. They should be merged into a single word.

How to Detect: –

Name: Long Sentence

Characteristic: *Granularity*

Scope: *Sentence*

Symptom: A sentence is relatively long to the other ones in a section. The target sentence may contain too much information or may contain unnecessary information, which decreases the understandability of the sentence. It should be separated so as to be easier to understand.

How to Detect: The number of characters in a sentence (length of a sentence) exceeds a threshold which is calculated by the distribution of the lengths of the sentences among the target use case description? (LOS > *Threshold_{Long}*)

Name: Short Sentence

Characteristic: *Granularity*

Scope: *Sentence*

Symptom: A sentence is relatively short to the other ones in a section. The target sentence may contain minor information or lack necessary information, which decreases the understandability of the sentence.

How to Detect: The number of characters in a sentence (length of a sentence) is less than a threshold which is calculated by the distribution of the lengths of the sentences among the target use case description? (LOS < *Threshold_{Short}*)

Name: Sentence with Multiple Actions

Characteristic: *Granularity*

Scope: *Sentence*

Symptom: A sentence denotes multiple actions. It should be assigned to a single action.

How to Detect: The number of action verbs in a sentence (NOV) exceeds to a threshold? (NOV > 4)

Name: Relatively Over Qualified Sentence

Characteristic: *Granularity*

Scope: *Sentence*

Symptom: A sentence has relatively many modifiers than other sentences. It may include irrelevant information to understand requirements.

How to Detect: The number of modifiers (NOM) exceeds a threshold which is calculated by the distribution of the numbers of the modifiers in sentences among the target use case description? (NOM > $Threshold_{OverModifier}$)

Name: Relatively Under Qualified Sentence

Characteristic: *Granularity*

Scope: *Sentence*

Symptom: A sentence has relatively fewer modifiers than other sentences. It may lack relevant information to understand requirements.

How to Detect: The number of modifiers (NOM) is less than a threshold which is calculated by the distribution of the numbers of the modifiers in sentences among the target use case description? (NOM < $Threshold_{UnderModifier}$)

Name: Omitting Pre-appeared Word

Characteristic: *Granularity*

Scope: *Word*

Symptom: A word appearing before is omitted in a sentence. Information related to the word may be lacking.

How to Detect: –

Name: Qualified Pre-appeared Word

Characteristic: *Granularity*

Scope: *Word*

Symptom: A word appearing before is qualified later, i.e., a word is not qualified at the first appearance, but it is qualified in the appearances after the first time. It means that relevant information that the word has was lacking when it appeared for the first time. When it appears at first, it should be qualified.

How to Detect: –

Name: Multiple Flows with the Same Role

Characteristic: *Redundancy*

Scope: *Flow*

Symptom: There are multiple flows whose goals are the same. It may cause the misunderstanding that these multiple flows may have a different meaning.

How to Detect: –

Name: Flow Unrelated to Postcondition

Characteristic: *Redundancy*

Scope: *Flow*

Symptom: Although the postconditions have already held, a flow performs actions not related to the postconditions. These actions may be redundant.

How to Detect: –

Name: Conditional Flow

Characteristic: *Redundancy*

Scope: *Flow*

Symptom: There is a flow where no actions are performed. It may not represent how to use the system to be developed, and can be considered redundant.

How to Detect: –

Name: Repeating the Same Noun

Characteristic: *Redundancy*

Scope: *Sentence*

Symptom: A sentence contains multiple occurrences of the same noun. Although the number of words in the sentence is increasing, there may be no new information obtained from the multiple occurrences of the noun.

How to Detect: The number of the occurrences of a noun in a sentence is more than 1? (NON(*noun*) > 1)

Name: Over-Qualified Word

Characteristic: *Redundancy*

Scope: *Word*

Symptom: The word *A* together with the modifier *B* appears in the description, but there are no occurrences of the single word *A* or none of the word *A* with the modifier different from *B*. In this case, it may cause the misunderstanding that the word *A* with the different modifier could be missing.

How to Detect: –

Name: Non-Standalone Use Case

Characteristic: *Lack*

Scope: *Usecase*

Symptom: A use case cannot be executed with a standalone. Another use case using it may be lacking.

How to Detect: –

Name: Missing Actor Section

Characteristic: *Lack*

Scope: *Section*

Symptom: There is no actor section in a use case. It is time-consuming to identify actors of the use case.

How to Detect: There is no Actor Section in the use case? ($\neg ActionSectionExist?$)

Name: Missing Exception Flows Section

Characteristic: *Lack*

Scope: *Section*

Symptom: There are no exception flow sections in a use case.
In this case, we have two alternatives; one is that the use case really has no exception flows, another is that there are no considerations on exception flows yet.
How to Detect: There is no exception flows in the use case?
(\neg ExceptionFlowSectionExist?)

Name: Missing Alternate Flows Section
Characteristic: *Lack*
Scope: *Section*

Symptom: There are no alternate flow sections in a use case.
In this case, we have two alternatives; one is that the use case really has no alternate flows, another is that there are no considerations on alternate flows yet.
How to Detect: There are no alternate flows in the use case?
(\neg AlternateFlowSectionExist?)

Name: Missing Preconditions Section
Characteristic: *Lack*
Scope: *Section*
Symptom: There is no section on preconditions. It is not clear when the use case can be executed.
How to Detect: There is not a precondition section in the use case?
(\neg PreconditionSectionExist?)

Name: Missing Postconditions Section
Characteristic: *Lack*
Scope: *Section*
Symptom: There is no section on postconditions. It is not clear what conditions should hold after the use case finishes its execution.
How to Detect: There is not a postcondition section in the use case?
(\neg PostconditionSectionExist?)

Name: Missing Description Section
Characteristic: *Lack*
Scope: *Section*
Symptom: There is no section on describing the overall of a use case. To understand what the use case do roughly, it is time-consuming because we should read all of the use case descriptions.
How to Detect: There is not a section on overall description of a use case?
(\neg OverviewSectionExist?)

Name: Missing Name Section
Characteristic: *Section*
Scope: *Section*
Symptom: There is no section to declare a use case name in a use case description. It is difficult to identify on which use case the descriptions are.
How to Detect: There is not a section declaring a use case name?
(\neg NameSectionExist?)

Name: Premature Exceptional Cases

Characteristic: *Lack*
Scope: *Flow*
Symptom: Every exceptional case that can occur is not described. It is not specified how to deal with the exceptional case that is not described.
How to Detect: –

Name: Premature Branch Condition
Characteristic: *Lack*
Scope: *Flow*
Symptom: Every alternative case that can occur is not described. It is not specified how to deal with the alternative case that is not described.
How to Detect: –

Name: Exception Flow without Return
Characteristic: *Lack*
Scope: *Sentence*
Symptom: There is no information on which sentence the execution returns to when the exception flow finishes, or on what terminate processing should be done after the exception flow. In this case, it is difficult to understand how to finish the use case correctly.
How to Detect: The sentence ID to which an exception flow returns is not specified?
(\neg ExceptionFlowsReturnExist?)

Name: Unexplained Exception Flow
Characteristic: *Lack*
Scope: *Sentence*
Symptom: There is no descriptions on the conditions which an exception can occur. It is difficult to understand why its basic flow is branched to the exception flow.
How to Detect: A condition where the exception occurs is not specified in a sentence?
(\neg ExceptionFlowsReasonExist?)

Name: Alternate Flow without Return
Characteristic: *Lack*
Scope: *Sentence*
Symptom: There is no information on which sentence the execution returns to when the alternate flow finishes, or on what terminate processing should be done after the alternate flow. In this case, it is difficult to understand how to finish the use case correctly.
How to Detect: The sentence ID to which an alternate flow returns is not specified?
(\neg AlternateFlowsReturnExist?)

Name: Unexplained Alternate Flow
Characteristic: *Lack*
Scope: *Sentence*
Symptom: There are no descriptions on the conditions which an alternative can occur. It is difficult to understand why its basic flow is branched to the alternate flow.

How to Detect: A condition where the alternative occurs is not specified in a sentence?
(\neg ExceptionFlowsReasonExist?)

Name: Incomplete System Behavior

Characteristic: *Lack*

Scope: *Sentence*

Symptom: Some of the system behavior to be required is not described. It is impossible to consider the function of the system correctly.

How to Detect: –

Name: Incomplete System Information

Characteristic: *Lack*

Scope: *Sentence*

Symptom: Some information necessary to implement the system is not described. It is difficult to implement the system correctly.

How to Detect: –

Name: Missing Action Target

Characteristic: *Lack*

Scope: *Word*

Symptom: A word that is a target of an action does not appear in a sentence. It is difficult to understand correctly how to use the system.

How to Detect: –

Name: Missing Operation Procedure

Characteristic: *Lack*

Scope: *Word*

Symptom: Some actual operations for the system are not described.

How to Detect: –

Name: Unknown Origin

Characteristic: *Lack*

Scope: *Word*

Symptom: There is no information on the source of newly generated information denoted by a word. It is difficult to check where the information is generated or to validate the correctness of the information.

How to Detect: –

Name: Precondition in Basic Flow

Characteristic: *Misplacement*

Scope: *Section*

Symptom: A precondition is described at the first step of the basic flow.

How to Detect: –

Name: Postcondition in Basic Flow

Characteristic: *Misplacement*

Scope: *Section*

Symptom: A postcondition is described at the last step of the basic flow.

How to Detect: –

Name: Exception Flow in Basic Flow

Characteristic: *Misplacement*

Scope: *Section*

Symptom: An exception flow is described in the basic flow. It is difficult to capture the essential behavior of the use case.

How to Detect: –

Name: Alternate Flow in Basic Flow

Characteristic: *Misplacement*

Scope: *Section*

Symptom: An alternate flow is described in the basic flow. It is difficult to capture the essential behavior of the use case.

How to Detect: –

Name: Synonym

Characteristic: *Inconsistency*

Scope: *Word*

Symptom: The different words having the same meaning is used.

How to Detect: –

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Seki, S. Hayashi, and M. Saeki, "Detecting bad smells in use case descriptions," to appear in *Proceedings of the 27th IEEE International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE'19)*, 2019.
- [2] R. Miles and K. Hamilton, *Learning UML 2.0: A Pragmatic Introduction to UML (Translated in Japanese)*. O'Reilly, 2007.
- [3] G. Schneider and J. P. Winters, *Applying Use Cases: A Practical Guide (Translated in Japanese)*. Pearson Education, 2000.
- [4] Y. Takaku, S. Hayashi, and M. Saeki, "Generating state transition models from use case descriptions," *IPSJ SIG Technical Reports*, vol. 2010-SE-167, no. 17, pp. 1–8, 2010.
- [5] K. T. Phalp, J. Vincent, and K. Cox, "Assessing the quality of use case descriptions," *Software Quality Journal*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 69–97, 2007.
- [6] F. Törner, M. Ivarsson, F. Pettersson, and P. Öhman, "Defects in automotive use cases," in *Proceedings of the 5th ACM/IEEE International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering (ISESE 2006)*, 2006, pp. 115–123.
- [7] B. Anda and D. I. K. Sjöberg, "Towards an inspection technique for use case models," in *Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on Software Engineering and Knowledge Engineering (SEKE 2002)*, 2002, pp. 127–134.

TABLE I
USE CASE DESCRIPTIONS USED FOR INSPECTION

ID	Name	Domain	Description	Source	B	E	A
U01	Move piece on board	Game	Move a piece in hand, take an enemy piece in the target space, or check the enemy king piece to take advantage	https://linuxserver.jp/%E8%A8%A8%E8%A8%88/uml/%E3%83%A6%E3%83%BC%E3%82%B9%E3%82%B1%E3%83%BC%E3%82%B9%E8%A8%98%E8%B0/ (S)+ (C)	5	8	2
U02	Print elderly relief call application form	Welfare	Register the elderly relief telephone application information in the system and output the "Relief telephone application form"	http://archive.city.yokohama.lg.jp/kenko/gohou/jiki-i-files/c02-sysuc-tb.pdf (S)+ (C)	9	6	0
U03	Display alarm at schedule time	Scheduler	Complete the attendance process	https://www.ogis-ri.co.jp/otc/hiroba/technical/JavaWorld_UML/chap5/ (S)+ (C)	4	0	1
U04	Process attendance	Business management	Complete the attendance process	http://objectclub.jp/technical/doc/uml/umlintro2 (S)+ (C)	6	2	0
U05	Operate wiper with washer	Automotive	Wash off oil film, mud, and insects	https://www.zipc.com/event/uc/18th_files/2/05-fujiwara.pdf (S)+ (C)	5	0	0
U06	Display	GUI	Display the table created by the actor	https://www.juse.or.jp/sqip/workshop/report/attachs/2008/5-testanalysis-appendix1.pdf (S)+ (C)	2	0	0
U07	Lend works to members	Rental	Lend works to members, collect the lending fee, and record the lending history	https://books.google.co.jp/books?id=Z3a1beWU1s&printsec=frontcover (S)+ (C)	18	6	5
U08	Draw shape	GUI	Re-register as a temporary user when the user has forgotten his/her password	http://www.fse.cs.ritsumei.ac.jp/lesson/java/practice2.html ² (S)+ (C)	5	0	1
U09	Load figures from file	GUI	Re-register as a temporary user when the user has forgotten his/her password	http://www.fse.cs.ritsumei.ac.jp/lesson/java/practice3.html ² (S)+ (C)	6	0	2
U10	Get emergency hospitalized	Welfare	Discard the order information entered by the customer	https://www.w.jahis.jp/... ^{*1} (S)+ (C)	10	0	0
U11	Daily home care	Welfare	Receive order details and register order information in the system	https://www.w.jahis.jp/... ^{*1} (S)+ (C)	19	0	0
U12	Discharge and transit to home care	Welfare	Create a sales order item and calculate the sales order amount with the products and quantities entered by the customer	https://www.w.jahis.jp/... ^{*1} (S)+ (C)	8	0	0
U13	Register user	Web	A user who wants to use the bulletin board registers his/her user information in the system	https://www.w.jahis.jp/... ^{*1} (S)+ (C)	13	4	0
U14	Register user officially	Web	A temporary user determines his/her official password and logs in to the system	https://www.ibm.com/developerworks/jp/websphere/library/java/web_practice/3.html (C)+ (U)	9	3	0
U15	Initialize password	Web	A user who wants to use the bulletin board registers his/her user information in the system	https://www.ibm.com/developerworks/jp/websphere/library/java/web_practice/4.html (C)+ (U)	8	2	0
U16	Log off	Shopping	Re-register as a temporary user when the user has forgotten his/her password	https://www.ibm.com/developerworks/jp/websphere/library/java/web_practice/5.html (C)+ (U)	8	2	0
U17	Register order information	Shopping	Discard the order information entered by the customer	https://www.ipa.go.jp/files/000056487.pdf (C)+ (U)	3	0	0
U18	Add item to cart	Shopping	Receive order details and register order information in the system	https://www.ipa.go.jp/files/000056487.pdf (C)+ (U)	10	0	5
U19	Search for product	Shopping	Create a sales order item and calculate the sales order amount with the products and quantities entered by the customer	https://www.ipa.go.jp/files/000056487.pdf (C)+ (U)	8	0	3
U20	Log on	Shopping	Display the product list by product category	https://www.ipa.go.jp/files/000056487.pdf (C)+ (U)	4	0	4
U21	Register user	Shopping	Authenticate the user and make the system available for him/her	https://www.ipa.go.jp/files/000056487.pdf (C)+ (U)	3	0	1
U22	Create new blog account	Web	Entering customer information, the system registers the user with the entered information and issues the user ID	https://www.ipa.go.jp/files/000056487.pdf (C)+ (U)	8	0	3
U23	Place order	Shopping	A new or existing author requests an administrator for a new blog account	Miles and Hamilton [2]	6	0	2
U24	Pay consumption tax	Shopping	Schneider and Winters [3]	Schneider and Winters [3]	9	0	1
U25	Update account	Shopping	Charge or transfer to an account	Schneider and Winters [3]	2	0	0
U26	Send product catalog	Shopping	A customer requests a product catalog	Schneider and Winters [3]	4	0	0
U27	Organize sales report	Shopping	Customer contact gets sales report	Schneider and Winters [3]	6	0	0
U28	Log in	Shopping	Customer contact gets sales report	Schneider and Winters [3]	5	0	0
U29	Log out	Shopping	Takaku <i>et al.</i> [4]	Takaku <i>et al.</i> [4]	2	0	1
U30	Order	Shopping	Takaku <i>et al.</i> [4]	Takaku <i>et al.</i> [4]	1	0	0
U31	Lend book	Rental	Takaku <i>et al.</i> [4]	Takaku <i>et al.</i> [4]	2	0	0
U32	Search for product	Shopping	Receptionist inputs to the system in the lending process	http://mysushi2011.appspot.com/ensyu_sakkei02.jsp (C)+ (U)	5	0	2
U33	Register product	Shopping	Display the product list by product category	https://blog.asial.co.jp/831 (S)+ (C)	3	3	0
U34	Withdraw money with ATM	Finance	Use the bank ATM to withdraw money from the account with a cash card	https://blog.asial.co.jp/831 (S)+ (C)	6	2	0
U35	Start care service	Welfare	An actor registers user information in the system as a temporary user	http://manomaru.web.fc2.com/examples/uml/ATMUsecase01.txt (S)+ (C)	10	4	6
U36	Register temporal user account	Web	An actor registers user information in the system as a temporary user	https://www.w.jahis.jp/... ^{*1} (S)+ (C)	12	0	0
U37	Register user account	Web	A user who wants to use the bulletin board registers his/her user information in the system	https://www.ibm.com/developerworks/jp/websphere/library/java/web_practice/3.html (C)+ (U)	8	2	0
U38	Purchase product	Shopping	A user who wants to use the bulletin board registers his/her user information in the system	https://www.ibm.com/developerworks/jp/websphere/library/java/web_practice/3.html (C)+ (U)	13	3	0
				https://qiita.com/putan/items/580c6c6f136859f82e6db (C)+ (U)	5	0	0

*1: Google Search, (C): Google Image Search, (U): Query of ["use case description", "welfare"]

*2: No longer available (accessed: 2019-07-05)

TABLE II
COMPARISON AMONG SMELL CATALOGUES

	P: Phalp <i>et al.</i> [5]	T: Tömer <i>et al.</i> [6]	A: Anda and Sjøberg [7]
S01: Unordered Flow	✓	✓	
S02: Origin-Free Exception Flow		✓	
S03: Origin-Free Alternative Flow		✓	
S04: Unclear Feasibility			
S05: Origin-Free Operation Result		✓	✓
S06: Sentence Interpretable as Multiple Meanings		✓	✓
S07: Pronoun		✓	✓
S08: Omitted Word		✓	✓
S09: "Actor" Actor		✓	✓
S10: Unexplained Main Actor		✓	✓
S11: Different Concepts by Same Word		✓	✓
S12: Omitted Attribute		✓	✓
S13: Flow Does Not Meet Precondition	✓	✓	✓
S14: Postcondition Not Satisfied	✓	✓	✓
S15: Name Does Not Explain Content	✓	✓	✓
S16: Under or Over Condition	✓	✓	✓
S17: Much or Less Actors	✓	✓	✓
S18: Contradicted Sentences	✓	✓	✓
S19: Behavior Ignores Condition	✓	✓	✓
S20: Multiple Situations		✓	✓
S21: Multiple Exception Flows at an Exception Branch Condition		✓	✓
S22: Multiple Alternate Flows at an Alternate Branch Condition			
S23: Multiple Roles of an Actor		✓	✓
S24: Multiple Actors of a Role		✓	✓
S25: Long Sentence	✓	✓	✓
S26: Short Sentence	✓	✓	✓
S27: Sentence with Multiple Actions	✓	✓	✓
S28: Relatively Over Qualified Sentence	✓	✓	✓
S29: Relatively Under Qualified Sentence	✓	✓	✓
S30: Omitting Pre-appeared Word	✓	✓	✓
S31: Qualified Pre-appeared Word	✓	✓	✓
S32: Multiple Flows with the Same Role	✓	✓	✓
S33: Flow Unrelated to Postcondition	✓	✓	✓
S34: Conditional Flow		✓	✓
S35: Repeating the Same Noun		✓	✓
S36: Over-qualified Word		✓	✓
S37: Non-Standalone Use Case		✓	✓
S38: Missing Actor Section		✓	✓
S39: Missing Exception Flows Section		✓	✓
S40: Missing Alternate Flows Section		✓	✓
S41: Missing Preconditions Section		✓	✓
S42: Missing Postconditions Section		✓	✓
S43: Missing Description Section		✓	✓
S44: Missing Name Section		✓	✓
S45: Premature Exceptional Cases		✓	✓
S46: Premature Branch Condition		✓	✓
S47: Exception Flow without Return		✓	✓
S48: Unexplained Exception Flow		✓	✓
S49: Alternative Flow without Return		✓	✓
S50: Unexplained Alternative Flow		✓	✓
S51: Incomplete System Behavior		✓	✓
S52: Incomplete System Information		✓	✓
S53: Missing Action Target		✓	✓
S54: Missing Operation Procedure		✓	✓
S55: Unknown Origin		✓	✓
S56: Precondition in Basic Flow		✓	✓
S57: Postcondition in Basic Flow		✓	✓
S58: Exception Flow in Basic Flow		✓	✓
S59: Alternate Flow in Basic Flow		✓	✓
S60: Synonym		✓	✓